

Topical electrospun patches loaded with oil for effective gamma linoleic acid transport and skin hydration towards atopic dermatitis skincare

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Polyimide
Electrospinning
Fibers
Gamma linoleic acid transport modeling
Skin hydration
Cell morphology

ABSTRACT

Atopic dermatitis is a common disease that affects around 20 % of children. One of the supportive therapies is long-term skin hydration which can be obtained by applying specially designed patches. Therefore, in this work, polyimide (PI) electrospun membranes as patches for atopic skin hydration were studied. PI fibers of diameter 500 ± 70 nm were assessed for biocompatibility using murine fibroblasts, NIH 3T3, and evaluated with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM), and MTS assay. The biocompatible PI membranes were mechanically tested and showed very high stretchability, above 350 %. These features, combined with a high membrane porosity of 95.6 %, make them excellent materials for skin patches. By loading the membranes with 10 μ l blackcurrant seed oil rich in 11–19 % of gamma linoleic acid (GLA), we obtained skin patches that allow long-term hydration. Patches were assessed *in vivo* with skin hydration tests over 6 h and compared to numerical simulation of GLA release to the skin. The results obtained indicate the great potential of the electrospun PI patches for atopic skin care applications.

1. Introduction

One of the most common inflammatory skin diseases that requires continuous care is atopic dermatitis. It affects up to 20% of children [1] and significantly decreases the patient's quality of life. The atopic skin is usually irritated with chronically relapsing inflammation, which causes an impaired barrier and increased transdermal absorption [2]. The atopic skin problem is inherently intractable because of the multifaceted etiology includes dysfunction of the natural skin barrier [3]. Among many reasons, there are genetic changes alterations in cell mediated immune responses. The distorted processing of proteins and enzymes leads to stratum corneum (SC) disruption. For instance, the enzyme delta-6-desaturase responsible for converting linoleic acid to gamma-linoleic acid (GLA) is deficient in patients with atopic dermatitis [4], therefore the amount is GLA is also decreased. For that reason, we focus on the GLA. The changes related to skin dysfunction are indicated by dysfunction of type 1 IgE antibodies and defects in cell-mediated immune responses. Next, a disrupted skin antimicrobial barrier not only causes water egress but also allows ingress of infection. To restore and protect the skin, barrier emollients, skin moisturizers [5] and natural oils such as borage [6], nigella sativa [7], blackcurrant seed (*Ribes*

Nigrum) [8], evening primrose [9], or hempseed [10] containing relatively high levels of beneficial GLA are used. Additionally, the wound healing activity of blackcurrant seed supported by its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activity is confirmed by *in vivo* study [11]. In fact, the blackcurrant seed oil is one of the richest oils in GLA [12], containing 10.9–16.7 % according to the fruit origin [13,14], or even up to 19 % [15]. Importantly, the delivery of GLA from blackcurrant seed oil has been confirmed *in vivo* orally [16] and transdermally [17,18]. To improve the atopic skin barrier, keeping the high skin hydration level is crucial, where GLA can obviously help. Aside from GLA, blackcurrant seed oil is also rich in essential fatty acids, tocopherols, phytosterols and triacylglycerols [13]. Delivering GLA to the atopic skin improves the skin barrier and reduces transepidermal water loss [19]. Sustained release of this substance can be achieved by incorporating it into the electrospun membrane [20]. Therefore, the focus of this study is on blackcurrant seed oil integrated with electrospun patches allowing the release of the oil in a desired and controlled manner through the skin surface. Such a solution has the advantage of a long-time moisturizing effect since the electrospun patches can be used as wound healing dressings, bandages, skin substitutes, or for tissue engineering [21–24].

Despite so many years dedicated to developing treatments for this

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.132256>

Received 13 July 2021; Received in revised form 17 August 2021; Accepted 1 September 2021

Available online 8 September 2021

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disorder, there are still many severe drawbacks and limitations. Primary therapy of atopic dermatitis is focused on topical skin hydration and avoidance of irritating factors, including topical application of corticosteroids supported by phototherapy [25]. For this study, we selected a polyimide (PI) material. The PI properties depend on the synthesis process—temperature, solvents, and reagents. In general, this is a robust material, thermally stable, resistant to most chemical reagents, oils and harsh environment, transparent to alpha and microwave radiation, and characterized by high tensile strength, toughness, and elastic modulus [26]. Therefore, PI is applied in microelectronics [27], display devices [28], food packaging [29], nuclear technology [30], fire retardant material [31], in aerospace and space-based industry [32], adhesives [33], flexible cables [34], or filters [35,36]. Furthermore, PI can be easily sterilized by ethanol, or UV-radiation. So far, PI has been investigated in the form of films [37] and used in implants [38] showing a great beneficial potential in using PI for biomedical applications. Also, electrospun PI fibers after the two-step synthesis revealed their biocompatibility [39]. In our study, we verified the biocompatibility of PI fibers obtained in the one-step electrospinning. This method allows obtaining electrospun membranes characterized with the high surface area to volume or mass ratio [40] and high porosity [41]. We investigated the PI porous patches for atopic skin hydration and care. The results obtained from PI membranes tested on human skin *in vivo*, were compared with a numerical simulation considering GLA concentration in blackcurrant seed oil and its transport through the membrane to the skin. PI membranes exhibited an excellent potential for atopic skin patches showing the hydration level for dry type of skin.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fibers and films production

Polyimide (PI P84) granulates provided by Ensinger Sintimid GmbH, Austria, were dried for 4 h at 50 °C (Drying Oven, POL-ECO Aparatura, Poland) to remove any residual water. The solution was prepared of PI (18 wt%) dissolved in a mixture of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and dimethylacetamide (DMAc) at mass ratio DMSO: DMAc = 3:7. The solvents in the analytical standard were purchased from Avantor, Poland.

The membrane was electrospun using a 21-gauge stainless steel needle kept at 15 cm from the collector with an applied voltage of 16 kV in equipment from IME Technologies (The Netherlands). The collector was rotational cylinder covered with a baking paper. The flow rate was 0.30 ml h⁻¹, and the membrane was deposited for 1.5 h. For mechanical testing PI fibers were collected on specially designed 20 × 8 mm laser-cut rectangular paper frames for 10 min [42]. The electrospinning climate control chamber conditions were set at RH = 60 % and T = 22 °C. For cell culture study reference samples, PI films were prepared on a glass slide using a spin-coater (L2001A v.3, Ossila, UK) at 6000 rpm for 60 s at RH = 50 % and T = 22 °C. The same PI solution was used for electrospinning and spin-coating.

2.2. Contact angles measurements

The contact angles of PI fibrous membranes and films were evaluated using water drops (3 μl, grade I) contour analysis on the samples' surfaces. The images were taken at RH = 40 % and T = 22 °C using a Canon EOS 700D camera with an EF-S 60 mm f/2.8 Macro USM zoom lens (Japan). The contact angles were determined from an average of 10 drops analyzed in ImageJ (J1.53v, National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, USA).

2.3. Mechanical testing

A tensile machine equipped with a 1 N cell (B.1708.A, Kammrath & Weiss, Germany) was used to mechanically characterize PI fibers, as

previously reported [43]. The experiments were performed at RH = 35 % and T = 24 °C. The extension rate was 25 μm s⁻¹. The average values of the maximum stress σ_{\max} , strain at maximum elongation ϵ_{\max} and strain at failure ϵ_f were calculated from 5 tests. Additionally, images of the membrane during the tensile testing were taken using the same camera and lens set-up used for contact angle experiments. The thickness of the samples was measured from cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Merlin Gemini II, ZEISS, Germany) images and confirmed by light microscope imaging in the z-direction (Axio Imager M1m, ZEISS, Germany)—see Figure S1.

2.4. Microscopy analysis

The morphology of PI samples was characterized using SEM (Merlin Gemini II, ZEISS, Germany). The samples were coated with a 10 nm layer of Au using a rotary pump sputter coater Q150RS (Quorum Technologies, UK). The membrane was imaged with 2–2.5 kV accelerating voltage, keeping current at 100 pA and the working distance at 4.5 mm, and the film imaged with the same voltage, 80 pA current, and the working distance 5.7 mm. The diameters of fibers d_f were obtained from the SEM images using ImageJ. The average diameter and its standard deviation were calculated from 100 randomly chosen fibers.

To obtain the 3D tomography of PI membranes, a sample was sliced and imaged using an SEM (FIB-SEM, Neon 40EsB CrossBeam, Carl Zeiss NTS GmbH, Germany), according to the methodology described in previous work [44]. The applied voltage for slicing the membrane was 30 kV, and the current was 100 pA. The voxel size obtained was 20 × 20 × 60 nm. To get the 3D reconstruction of electrospun PI nanofibers, a stack of 93 images obtained from FIB-SEM using Avizo Fire 6.1 (Amira, FEI, USA) was aligned. This alignment corrects the angle (52°) arising from the observation tilt. In the following reconstruction steps, fiber marking slice by slice was performed manually. The volume and membrane porosity were calculated from the model obtained using the statistical tool in Avizo Fire 6.1.

2.5. Biocompatibility

Biocompatibility tests were performed on NIH 3T3 murine fibroblasts (Sigma Aldrich, UK) at 2 × 10⁴ cells per well in 24-well plates. We assessed PI porous membranes and films biocompatibility, as blackcurrant seed oil is a natural oil which is edible. Cell culture was conducted over 7 days using Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) supplemented with bovine serum (10 %), antibiotics (penicillin/streptomycin, 2 %), amino acids (1 %), and L-glutamine (1 %, Sigma Aldrich, UK). The cell culture was conducted under standard conditions (T = 37 °C, RH = 90 % and 5 % CO₂ at atmospheric pressure). Tissue culture polystyrene (TCPS) was used for the positive control. The cell culture medium was changed after 3 days, and the condition of the cells was checked after 1, 3, and 7 days.

Cell morphology was investigated with SEM. The culture medium was removed after each measuring time point. The samples were washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and fixed for SEM observation with formaldehyde solution (4.5 %, Sigma Aldrich, UK) for 30 min at 4 °C. Afterward, the samples were dehydrated in a series of ethanol solutions (50 %, 70 %, 96 %, and ~ 99.9 %, Avantor, Poland)—three times in each concentration solution for 3 min. Finally, these dehydrated samples were immersed in hexamethyldisilazane (Sigma Aldrich, UK) under a fume hood and left to dry overnight. The scaffolds with cells were prepared for SEM imaging, as described in the microscopy analysis section.

For the confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM), the cells on PI samples were fixed with 4 % paraformaldehyde solution for 60 min at 4 °C, and then permeabilized with 0.1 % Triton X-100 in PBS for 5 min at 25 °C. Next, the cells were incubated in a blocking solution (3 % bovine serum albumin in PBS) for 1 h. Finally, to visualize actin filaments, cells were incubated for 1 h at T = 23 °C with Alexa Fluor™ 633 Phalloidin

(ThermoFisher, USA). The cell nuclei were also stained with DAPI for 5 min. A Zeiss LSM 900 confocal microscope (Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, Germany) was used to image cells using ZEN 3.1 software (Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, Germany) and they were processed with ImageJ software. The following microscopy parameters were used: Plan-Apochromat 63x/1.4 Oil DIC M27, confocal iris set at 1 Airy disc, pixel size 70 nm, pixel time 4.70 μ s, excitation 488 nm and 633 nm, emission detection bands 410–570 nm for DAPI and 645–700 nm for Alexa Fluor™ 633 coupled with Phalloidin. Registration in a sequential mode was performed with 4 averaged frames for one confocal plane. The cell proliferation was evaluated by colorimetric measurement of MTS assay (CellTiter 96 Aqueous One Solution Cell Proliferation Assay, Promega, USA). The quantity of formazan produced was measured by the amount of 490 nm absorbance on 96-well plates using a spectrophotometer (Microplate Reader LT-4000, Labtech International Ltd., UK). The raw absorbance data were normalized to the corresponding sample surface area.

2.6. Water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) measurements

WVTRs were measured for the neat PI membranes and the membranes with 10 μ l of blackcurrant seed oil, where the medical gauze was used as control samples. The glass beakers were filled with the distilled water (5 ml, grade I) and tightly wrapped with these patches. The beakers were kept over 24 h in the water bath of 37 °C at RH in range 40–50 %. By weighting the beakers, the WVTRs were calculated as the water loss [g] per evaporation exposure area [m²] per day. The statistics was performed from 3 replicates of each sample.

2.7. Oil release according to applied pressure

The maximum oil uptake was calculated by taking the PI membrane porosity and the membrane dimensions (3 × 3 cm, thickness 275 ± 24 μ m). For this experiment, 100 % of the maximum porous space was filled with blackcurrant seed oil, reaching 240 μ l. This oil volume was pipetted onto the PI membrane and afterward moved to the adsorbing tissue made from pure flax pulp (shine control tissues, Theatric Professional, Poland). Then, additional pressure was applied with the calibrated weights on plates. After 3 h, the membranes and tissues were weighed using a laboratory balance (Pioneer PA214CM/1 OHAUS Europe GmbH, Switzerland). From these data, the membrane oil retention and release percentages were calculated.

2.8. Human skin hydration – in vivo tests

The testing of the patches on human skin were performed on volunteers following the ethical considerations with respect to human testing of cosmetic products guidelines by EU according to the Council Directive (76/768/EEC) and World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki (1964–1975–1983–1989–1996). First, the human leg skin *in vivo* was gently washed with neutral pH soap. The patches are designed for long-term usage; therefore, the minimum sleep time for adults equal to 6 h was selected for the tests. The experiments were performed on 6 volunteers, both females, and males, of Caucasian race aged 22–54 years, with healthy skin. The membranes used in the skin tests were approximately 275 μ m thick. After placing the PI membrane on the shin skin and taping the edges with tape, 10 μ l of blackcurrant seed oil was pipetted on it. The skin hydration was measured with a corneometer (Hydro Pen H10, Medelink, CA) 5 times in each testing place before and after patch application. Additionally, the reference PI patch without oil was applied as a control, and the control skin hydration was measured every hour for 6 h. The difference in skin hydration was calculated as a simple difference between the value after and before the patch test, with deviation recalculated as standard uncertainty.

2.9. Numerical simulation of GLA transport

The simulation of GLA transport from porous PI membrane to the skin was performed using COMSOL Multiphysics (version 5.6, COMSOL Inc., Sweden). In the mathematical model, all the voids in the PI membrane were filled with blackcurrant seed oil. The membrane model consisted of one slice of the YZ plane from a reconstructed spatial model replicated 38 times to reach a total height 274.51 μ m. The three-layer skin model was simplified in the simulation [45] to two layers, SC (a topical/surface part of the epidermis) and epidermis, considered two homogeneous layers. The homogenous model of the skin is proved to work well and is commonly used in mathematical models [46].

According to the literature, the GLA mass concentration in blackcurrant seed oil is 10.9–19.0 % [13–15]. The average of this range was taken; thus 15.0 % GLA in blackcurrant seed oil was used for simulation purposes, and the mass concentration recalculated as 571.1 mol m⁻³. Additionally, the GLA diffusion coefficient (*D*) was calculated from Eq. (1):

$$D = \frac{h_{skin}^2}{t_{lag}} \quad (1)$$

where h_{skin} is the corresponding skin layer thickness, and t_{lag} is the lag time calculated as the intercept of the regression line on the time axis in the plot of released GLA against time [46]. In the literature, the SC thickness of leg skin is estimated as 22.0 ± 6.9 μ m [47], or 22.4 ± 2.2 μ m [48], and the shin epidermis thickness is 63.4 ± 8.2 μ m [49]. Generally, the skin thickness depends on the skin condition, hydration, age, gender, and health but, in numerical simulation, the average values of SC as 22.1 μ m and epidermis as 63.4 μ m were used. Skin desquamation was not included in the computer simulation; even though, in diseased skin, its desquamation significantly affects the skin percutaneous transport.

The lag time for SC was measured for other natural oils and is in the range of 0.6–2.2 h [50]. The average value of 1.2 h for the most concentrated oil solutions was used and recalculated for the SC diffusion coefficient $D_{SC} = 1.9 \times 10^{-14}$ m² s⁻¹. Based on previous research where the lag times of 50 compounds relevant to cosmetics ingredients for various skin layers were compared [51], the average diffusion coefficient ratio $D_{SC} : D_{epi} = 0.14 \pm 0.06$ was estimated. From this relation and the SC diffusion coefficient value, the epidermis diffusion coefficient was estimated as $D_{epi} = 1.3 \times 10^{-13}$ m² s⁻¹, and this value was used in the simulation. The numerical simulation was calculated from Eq. (2) and Eq. (3):

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \nabla J = R \quad (2)$$

where *c* is GLA concentration [mol m⁻³], *t* is time [s], *J* is mass flux [mol m⁻² s⁻¹], and *R* means the reaction rate for the GLA source term [mol m⁻³ s⁻¹].

$$J = -D\nabla c \quad (3)$$

The standard temperature for such calculations is 32 °C [52,53] as human skin temperature, but a more accurate one was taken- calves skin temperature as 31.6 °C [54]. The calculations are performed under constant atmospheric pressure. Three computing step sizes (Figure S2) and three numerical grids (Figure S3) were compared to obtain results independent of the numerical parameters. The optimal simulation parameters were step size $\Delta t = 0.1$ s in the range from 0 to 1 s, $\Delta t = 10$ s in the range 1 to 21 600 s; triangular mesh with elements size in the range 0.1–1.0 μ m, maximum growth rate equal 1.2 and curvature factor 0.5. The mesh consisted of 926 589 triangle elements, its minimum orthogonal quality was 0.3677, and average quality 0.8351. The model dimensions were 17.72 × 360.01 μ m in total (PI membrane: 274.51 μ m, SC: 22.13 μ m, epidermis: 63.37 μ m). In the present case, the step size is important while the mesh size is of minor significance, see Figure S4, model mesh for the simulation.

Fig. 1. PI fibrous membrane characterization: (a) SEM micrograph of PI membrane surface and (b) single fibers from PI membrane; (c) distribution histogram of PI fiber diameter in the electrospun PI membrane; (d) 3D reconstruction of electrospun PI membrane with voxel size of $20 \times 20 \times 60 \text{ nm}$; photos of the PI membrane taken during the tensile testing showing the alignment of electrospun fibers due to the extension at (e) – 0 %, (f) – 125 %, (g) – 250 %, (h) – 375 % strain (the red parts in the pictures are the paper frame on which the PI fibers were deposited during electrospinning); (i) the stress – strain curves from 5 tensile tests of PI electrospun membranes. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2.10. Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis of the results from the tensile testing and from the fibers diameters measurements were performed using OriginPro (2019 SR1, OriginLab, USA). The MTS test results and results from skin hydration *in vivo* experiments were statistically investigated using Statistica (13.3, StatSoft, Inc., USA) at the significance level $p = 0.05$. Shapiro-Wilk test dedicated to small size groups was performed. For a

few MTS data and a few volunteers evaluated for skin hydration level (a, e) Shapiro-Wilk test results indicated p -values below 0.05, which means these data sets were not characterized by a normal distribution. Therefore, for them non-parametric tests were applied in further steps. For MTS the Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed that the differences between groups investigated were statistically significant. For normal distributions of the skin hydration data (volunteer b-d, f), the parametric tests were performed- ANOVA with Tukey post-hoc assay. The statistical

Fig. 2. The results showing the PI biocompatibility. SEM micrographs of fibroblasts PI fibers after (a) 1, (b) 3 and (c) 7 days in culture and similarly CLSM images of fibroblasts on the PI fibers after (d) 1, (e) 3 and (f) 7 days in culture; (g) MTS assay results assessing the fibroblasts proliferation on PI fibers and films compared with TCPS; (h) cross-section of cell between fibers after 7th day of incubation; SEM micrographs of fibroblasts on PI films after (i) 1, (j) 3 and (k) 7 days of culture and similarly CLSM images on the PI film after (l) 1, (m) 3 and (n) 7 days. In all CLSM images the nuclei were stained with DAPI (blue) and the actin filaments with Alexa Fluor™ 633 Phalloidin (red). *statistical significance calculated with Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by Shapiro-Wilk test, $p < 0.05$. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

evaluation of the skin hydration level data is enclosed in the [Figure S5](#).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of PI fibers

PI was successfully electrospun to produce uniform membranes with an average fiber diameter of 500 ± 70 nm, see SEM images in [Fig. 1a–b](#), similar to a previous study [26]. The 3D reconstruction of PI electrospun membrane ([Fig. 1d](#)) allowed calculation of the volume of fibers, which reached $31.70 \mu\text{m}^3$ out of the total reconstruction volume of $716.68 \mu\text{m}^3$, giving a membrane porosity of 95.6%. Importantly, this high porosity is beneficial because the spaces between fibers can be filled with natural oils such as blackcurrant seed oil. [Video S1](#) in [Supplementary Information](#) (SI) represents the animation of PI membrane 3D reconstruction. A

SEM image of PI film can be found in [Figure S6](#). The wetting properties of the electrospun membranes are important for skin patches applications [55]. The water contact angle of PI fibrous membranes was $134 \pm 2^\circ$ and for the PI film: $57 \pm 1^\circ$. We confirmed the hydrophobicity of PI fibers [56] and the hydrophilic character of PI films [57]. Pictures of water droplets are presented in [Figure S7](#). The PI membranes were tensile tested, with the stress–strain curves shown in [Fig. 1i](#), indicating their large extension due to the alignment of PI fibers in the randomly electrospun mats. The average value of the maximum stress σ_{max} was 11.4 ± 1.1 kPa at the average strain ϵ_{max} of 93.9 ± 5.6 %. The maximum elongation ϵ_f was 373.6 ± 1.2 %; however, due to the equipment limitation, not all the PI fibers in the membrane were ruptured. The mechanical testing of the PI membrane indicates very high stretchability, see [Video S2](#) in [Supplementary Information](#). As long as the randomly oriented fibers were extended, they slid on each other and aligned in the

Fig. 3. Water vapor transmission rates through gauze, PI membrane and PI membrane with blackcurrant seed oil measured after 24 h.

stretching direction, enhancing their mechanical performance [58] as well as changing their pore shape and size [59]. Previously, the PI films were tested, showing maximum strain in the range 7.7–16.6 % and maximum stress of 84.5–121.6 MPa [60]. The enhanced stretchability of the PI fibrous membranes makes them a perfect candidate for skin bandages since the stretchability of PI membranes is greater than the stretchability of the skin. The mechanical properties of skin depend strongly on the skin condition, age, body place, medical history, race, gender. But the estimated human skin failure stretch value is in range 37–71 % [61]. Therefore, the high stretchability of electrospun PI patches do not limit the patient's movements and are comfortable to apply and wear.

3.2. Biocompatibility

We verified the biocompatibility of PI fibers and compared with PI film. The SEM observations allowed evaluation of the cellular attachment and anchoring to the PI fibers (Fig. 2a–c) and films (Fig. 2i–k), and also the CLSM imaging of cells on the PI fibrous membrane and film, as presented in Fig. 2d–f and Fig. 2l–n. PI polymer shows the ability to emit significant fluorescent signals after laser irradiation with wavelengths 405 nm and 633 nm without cells and medium, see Figure S8. For that reason, during fluorescent imaging of cell nuclei and actin filaments, a significant visible background signal in both channels was observed from PI fibers and the PI film. The fibroblasts anchored to the PI fibers from the 1st day (Fig. 2a), and a large number stayed on their surface but without being significantly elongated or adhering to the base surface (Fig. 2d). Cells grew at random locations on the whole samples, and cell clusters were not observed. In Fig. 2b and Fig. 2e, fibroblasts started to adhere very well to fibrous membranes after the 3rd day. The cells spread around the fibrous membrane and created agglomerates and colonies with increased formation of filopodia. After the 7th day (Fig. 2c, f), the cells were more elongated in one common direction despite the random distribution of PI fibers. However, the cross-section of the NIH 3T3 fibroblast (Fig. 2h) shows cell growth between the PI fibers, indicating the advantage of fibers over films for cell integration with the material. Similar observations were made for PI film on the 1st day of incubation (Fig. 2i, l). They formed filopodia anchored to the particles on the film surface (see Figure S6), where cells were organized into small 2-cell colonies. From the 3rd day, the fibroblasts continued proliferating

Fig. 4. a) The blackcurrant seed oil release from electrospun PI membrane after 3 h on the absorbing tissue depending on the applied pressure. The images of spreading of blackcurrant seed oil from PI membrane on the absorbing tissue depending on the applied pressure in time up to 3 h: (b–e) no additional pressure, (f–i) additional pressure applied by 40 g weight through aluminum plate. The images of oil spreading are taken immediately after oil application ($t = 0$ h), after 1 h ($t = 1$ h) and 3 h ($t = 3$ h), as indicated on the left side of the images.

on the PI film (Fig. 2j, m), with numerous colonies appearing. After the 7th day of incubation, the fibroblasts were fully integrated with the membrane surface, having created an extensive monolayer on the PI membrane and film (Fig. 2c, f, k, n). Typically, fibroblasts proliferate rapidly on flat and smooth surfaces [62], but that depends greatly on the material morphology and the surface chemistry [63]. Undoubtedly, the cells in both cases present typical fibroblastic morphology such as elongation and numerous focal adhesions, indicating high biocompatibility of PI membranes. PI membrane is an excellent material for fibroblast growing due to its small fiber diameter and low surface roughness

Fig. 5. The human leg skin *in vivo* hydration values (a-f) for each volunteer, age from 22 to 54 years female and male, before and after application of PI patch with blackcurrant seed oil from 1 h to 6 h measured every hour. The control is PI membrane without blackcurrant seed oil measured after 6 h. (g) The representative image of the experimental arrangements of the patches on the volunteers.

[64].

From the fibroblast viability assay, MTS, higher absorbance values were observed for all PI samples after 7 days of cell culture, see Fig. 2g. The MTS results indicated that, on the 1st incubation day, the absorbance value was very similar for all samples. After the 3rd day of culture, the number of fibroblasts was almost unchanged for the PI fibers and slightly higher for the PI film, showing hydrophilic behavior, see Figure S7. The TCPS absorbance value was much higher than for PI samples and much higher than on the 1st day. On the 7th day, the highest proliferation level was observed for PI film, less for TCPS and least for PI fibers, indicating the non-cytotoxicity effect of PI samples. We conclude that the absorbance value shows the non-cytotoxicity of PI membrane and film, similarly to the previous tests [39,65]. Regardless of the expected higher cell proliferation on PI film, the high biocompatibility of PI membranes was proven, showing their potential applicability in medical applications.

3.3. Water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) results

WVTR results are presented in the Fig. 3. The high porosity of PI membranes reaching 95.6 % results in higher permeability than gauze which is used as a reference material in the control experiments [55]. The addition of blackcurrant seed oil to the PI membrane reduces the permeability to the similar values as obtained for a gauze still allowing free gas exchange while used as a skin dressing.

3.4. Oil release tests

The PI membranes are excellent oil reservoirs due to their high porosity. The oil release from the patches can be enhanced after applying a pressure to them, therefore we verified the effect of applied pressure on blackcurrant seed oil release on the absorbing tissue from patches as presented in Fig. 4. In Fig. 4a the plot shows that the higher the applied pressure, the more oil was released. The pictures of released oil on the absorbing tissue are shown in Fig. 4b-i. Interestingly, even under the highest applied pressure of 101.8 kPa in this experiment, the oil was not fully released, and some was remaining in the patches. This is very promising result from the practical point of view, as the typical

pressure on the part of the body lying under its own weight is between 101.4 and 101.6 kPa. Clearly, applying pressure is able to enhance the patch effectiveness as more oil with GLA is released from the membrane in shorter time, still living the remains to be delivered in the standard diffusion process.

The PI membranes with blackcurrant seed oil were also tested on healthy human skin *in vivo* on 6 volunteers. The results of the skin hydration after PI patch applications are presented in Fig. 5. To maintain graphs' clarity, statistical evaluation has been summarized in Figure S5 in the Supplementary Information. The first value is a control measurement patch without oil. Importantly, we observed that the PI patches with oil increased skin hydration, see Fig. 5. The overall trend is that the longer patch is applied, the higher the increase in skin hydration observed. After 3 h of patch application the SC saturation with oil is observed- the skin hydration is kept at similar level, likewise the previous experiments on drug delivery [66]. GLA saturates the SC and afterwards comes to deeper skin layers. Blackcurrant seed oil is a mixture of different compounds [13] and GLA easily penetrates intact skin, whereas other heavier oil components do not penetrate and contribute skin occlusion. That increase water retention in SC is also beneficial for atopic skin. It is claimed that skin hydration level below 30 % occurs for very dry skin, between 30 and 40 % for dry and above 40 % for normal skin [67]. The highest differences between skin hydration values before and after patch application were observed for the very dry skin case (Fig. 5c). It was noticeable that the initial skin hydration depends on the tests locations; therefore, the skin hydration results varied after the patch application. Overall, the applied patches improve skin condition; however, the basic therapy and additional long-term patch usage must be implemented. Importantly, the skin hydration increase is dependent on the initial skin hydration level. These results provide direct evidence that the proposed PI membranes with blackcurrant seed oil are an excellent material for skin patches.

3.5. Numerical simulation of GLA

The patients with atopic dermatitis have a deficiency of GLA in the skin, therefore we modeled the GLA mass transport through the PI patches with blackcurrant seed oil. The electrospun PI membrane was

Fig. 6. (a–d) GLA concentration distribution over 6 h in the SC (lower layer in the model) and 275 μm PI membranes loaded with blackcurrant seed oil (upper layer in the model, only fragments of the membranes shown), where the black dots are cross-sections of PI nanofibers; (e) The graph shows the GLA concentration depending on the layer setup taken across the model centrally in the vertical direction. $I_{\text{SC-oil}}$ means the interphase boundary between SC and PI membrane.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the numerical simulation of the GLA delivery to the SC surface for different membrane thicknesses with the experimental data for volunteer c. Δ skin hydration was calculated as the difference between values of hydration after and before patch application.

reconstructed based on the FIB-SEM images (Fig. 1d) placed directly on the skin model consisting of the top two layers: SC and epidermis. The PI patches reaching 95.6 % porosity were filled with blackcurrant seed oil

containing 15 % GLA. In the model domain, the mass transport is mainly by diffusion [46], with the diffusion coefficient determining the diffusion flux [68]. However, the main driving force for GLA transport is its concentration gradient between the blackcurrant seed oil and the skin. The results are shown in Fig. 6, focused on the diffusion through the membrane to the top layer of the skin (SC). At the very beginning (Fig. 6a), no release was observed. Almost all the GLA remained in the PI membrane up to 30 s, where only a thin diffusion layer is visible in the interphase boundary between the PI membrane and the SC ($I_{\text{SC-oil}}$). Over time, the concentration gradient decreased, and the GLA moved across the membrane and the skin. Even after 6 h (Fig. 6d), not all GLA had gone to the skin, and some remained in the PI membrane. The GLA was distributed along with the deeper skin layers; therefore, it gradually disappeared from the top layer (SC). To see the full results, the quantitative representation of the GLA concentration dependence on the release time and the distance from the skin surface is shown. In Fig. 6, the plots presented are taken across the model centrally in the vertical direction. The PI patches are designed for long-term oil release, and the simulation showed the increase of GLA passing from oil to the skin.

These simulation results, Fig. 6, were confirmed with *in vivo* tests, Fig. 5, indicating significant skin hydration increase already after 3 h, as shown previously [55,69]. Fig. 7 compares the simulated GLA transport and the *in vivo* test on the volunteer c with the lowest initial hydration skin levels (21 ± 7 %, very dry skin), indicating typical atopic skin problems [70]. The GLA concentration was taken from the top of the SC

layer (point $x = -5 \mu\text{m}$) as this skin position was measured experimentally. The model confirms that the GLA transport is directly related to and responsible for increase in skin hydration. The increasing trend of skin hydration is directly correlated with the GLA transport, reaching its maximum after 3 h from applying the PI patch with blackcurrant seed oil. Both experimental and numerical results in 3 h point show the beginning of a plateau level when the SC becomes saturated with GLA [66], and the applied patch hydrates the skin. In the model, the amount of GLA in the patch was directly correlated with the membrane thickness as it is fully filled with the oil. In the model, exactly the same membrane thickness was used in order to compare the skin hydration level in the *in vivo* experiment. The effect of the patch thickness on the skin hydration is shown in Figure S9. The thinner membrane (29 μm) is enough for skin hydration, and the numerical simulation results are similar for both thicknesses. The thicker PI membrane (275 μm) is, however, easier to apply and gives better skin protection. Additionally, more oil placed in the thicker membrane can be released under extra pressure applied to the patch if necessary. The designed PI patches are suitable for long-term applications, for example, overnight, due to keeping the highest hydration level up to 6 h *in vivo* tests correlated with the continuous GLA transport over that time. Additional pressure on patches is desirable and reached while lying (for example the additional pressure of 0.15 kPa can be obtained by own weight of the calf) and involuntary movements during sleep. The additional pressure increases the amount of oil delivered to the skin, enhancing skin hydration. Currently on the market there are only beauty masks based on electrospun for moisturizing effect that often are dissolved after applying water [71,72].

4. Conclusions

PI is a stable material, resistant to oils and most chemical reagents. Importantly, we showed that electrospun PI patches are biocompatible, highly porous (95.6 %), and stretchable. These membranes are excellent materials for skin patches as they adjust to skin movements simultaneously stretch, letting air exchange due to their high permeability and suitable WVTR. Atopic dermatitis usually occurs inside the elbows and behind the knees, where the skin is often bent. Therefore, the high elasticity of PI membranes is the prime advantage that allows using these membranes as patches for skincare and treatment.

PI patches with blackcurrant seed oil rich in GLA are perfect for long-term application and were tested up to 6 h. The oil release can be additionally enhanced with applied pressure to the patch. The atopic skin numerical model was developed and used for analysis of GLA transports from PI patches with blackcurrant seed oil to the skin. The numerical simulation confirmed that the longer the patch is applied, the more GLA is delivered to the atopic skin deficient in this compound. The modeling of GLA transport confirmed the *in vivo* experiments showing the direct increase in the skin hydration especially for very dry skin, representing the atopic skin. The modeling allows to optimize the PI patch application for atopic skin hydration and develop further individually tailored therapy for atopic dermatitis treatment or effective skincare. Summarizing, the obtained experimental results confirmed with computer modeling, allow further development of patches with the skin hydration effect designed according to the patient's needs. Future experiments will be conducted on patients suffering from atopic dermatitis.

Author contribution

Author contributions: E.A.S. designed, performed and analyzed the experiments, all simulations and wrote the paper; K. B. imaged samples with CLSM and interpreted the results; M.J. supervised the numerical simulations; U.S. secured resources, supervised the research, designed the experiments and wrote the paper. All authors analyzed the data and proofread the manuscript.

Data and materials availability: all data needed to evaluate the

conclusions in the paper are present in the paper and the Supplementary Information. Additional data related to this paper may be requested from the authors upon reasonable request.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

Funding: this study was conducted within "Nanofiber-based sponges for atopic skin treatment" project carried out within the First Team program of the Foundation for Polish Science co-financed by the European Union under the European Regional Development Fund, project no POIR.04.04.00-00- 4571/17-00. We thank all volunteers for their contribution to the study and Adam Gruszczyński for FIB-SEM tomography of the PI membrane.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.132256>.

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